

FEM ANALYSIS OF MICRO-INDENTATION TEST FOR C/C COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: To investigate the mechanism of energy loss in load - displacement of indenter curve (indentation curve) under fiber indentation test of unidirectionally reinforced C/C composites, the fiber indentation tests were performed and the indentation curve was analyzed by an axis symmetrical finite-element method (FEM) model including a newly designed fiber-matrix interfacial bonding. In this model, only elastic deformations were considered for both fiber and matrix, and the interfacial bonding was assumed to yield not to fracture. From this FEM analysis, a hysteresis loop was obtained in the indentation curve and the interfacial debonding was founded to start from the inside of specimen under the indentation test. And the indentation curve calculated by the FEM analysis was coincide with the experimental results, so compressive Young's modulus of carbon fiber in C/C composite was founded to be predictable from the FEM analysis.

KEYWORDS: C/C composite, carbon fiber, indentation test, interface, finite element method, Young's modulus, transmission electron microscopy, graphite

INTRODUCTION

Mechanical properties of interface between fibers and matrices are known to be quite influential in determining properties of fiber reinforced composites. Some of the previous reports have indicated the effectiveness of controlling fiber-matrix interface on improving properties of composite materials [1]. So the effects of surface treatment or coating on fibers for several composites have been studied [2] and many experiments have been carried out to measure the interfacial mechanical properties by various methods, those were pull-out test [3], push-out test [4], protrusion test [5] and multiple fracture test [6]. And most of these studies have done by using simple model composites reinforced with single thick fiber. But practical carbon reinforced carbon (C/C) composites are reinforced with a large number of very thin fibers and have many pores and cracks in matrix [7]. Therefore, to measure the mechanical properties of practical C/C composites in the micro area is very difficult and the micro indentation test is considered to be one of the suitable test method.

There were some reports of the indentation tests about carbon materials [8], but in these reports maximum load and displacement of indenter were too large to indent only one fiber in

the practical C/C composites. So, to study mechanical properties of fiber, matrix and their interface in C/C composites, the authors have applied a newly developed ultra micro indentation test machine to fiber indentation tests in C/C composites [9-11]. Where, any indications of plastic deformation were not observed on specimen surfaces after indentation test by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), although load - displacement of indenter curve (indentation curve) showed large hysteresis loop, that indicated the existence of some energy loss under the test [10]. However this experimental result could not be understood by any models including the indentation tests of carbon materials as far as the authors knowledge. So, in this study, fiber indentation tests were performed and a new finite-element method (FEM) model was provided for analyzing the deformations of fiber, matrix and their interface.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material Used and Specimen

Material used was unidirectionally reinforced C/C composite, heat treated at 1873 K. Carbon fiber used was mesophase pitch-based fiber and its characteristics are shown in Table 1. Matrix precursor was a mixture of green coke and phenolic resin (80/20 in volumetric ratio). And a fiber volume fraction and a density of C/C composite were 45.0 % and 1.69 Mg/m³, respectively.

Table 1: Characteristics of fibers used

Diameter (μm)	9.8
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	542
Tensile Strength (Gpa)	2.92
Heat Treatment Temperature (K)	2473

Schematic flow of specimen preparation for fiber indentation test is shown in Fig. 1. C/C specimen, whose size was $20^l \times 5^w \times 1^t$ mm, was fixed at the center of acrylic pipe by resin. And next, the fixed specimen was sliced perpendicular to the fiber direction with about 200 μm thickness by low speed diamond saw. Then the thickness of sliced specimen was reduced 80 μm by mechanical grinding and the pipe and resin were removed in acetone. Finally the size of specimen for fiber indentation test became $5^l \times 1^w \times 0.08^t$ mm.

Fig. 1: Schematic flow of specimen preparation and shape of indentation tip

Fiber Indentation Test

Fiber indentation tests were carried out by utilizing the dynamic ultra indentation test machine [8]. The specimen was placed on a specimen holder made of SUS and fibers in C/C composites were loaded by triangular diamond pyramid indenter tip, where maximum loads were 0.2 N. The shape of triangular diamond pyramid indenter tip is shown in Fig. 1. The inclination angle of side triangle was 68 degrees.

Structural Inspections

Macroscopic structure, including fiber volume fraction, was determined by both optical microscopy and SEM. And microstructural inspections of interface were performed with high resolution transmission electron microscopy (TEM : JEOL-4000FX), where an acceleration voltage was 400 kV. Specimens for TEM observation were prepared by dimple grinding and Ar ion milling, and were observed parallel to the fiber direction.

RESULTS OF FIBER INDENTATION TEST

Typical examples of indentation curves under fiber indentation tests are shown in Fig. 2. For all cases, the indentation curves showed large hysteresis loops and came back to the origin. Under indentation tests of glasslike carbon, same hysteresis loops were reported [8]. However maximum load and displacement of indenter were over 10 N and 100 μm under the carbon indentation test, respectively. In addition to that, cracks were observed at the specimen surface after carbon indentation tests by SEM. But, after the fiber indentation tests, the interfacial debonding and the indentation mark could not be observed at the specimen surface. It indicates that the origin of the hysteresis loops under the fiber indentation tests was different from that under the carbon indentation tests, that is, the loops under the fiber indentation tests were not resulted from the essential property of carbon.

And micro steps can be detected in Fig. 2 and some of them are pointed out by arrows, those are considered to be indications of interfacial debonding. So, for the exact understanding of the indentation curves and the deformations of fiber, matrix and interface in C/C composites under fiber indentation test, a new FEM analysis including the interfacial debonding seems to be needed.

Fig. 2: Indentation curves under fiber indentation test in C/C composites

FEM MODEL

Shape of FEM Model

By using an axis symmetrical FEM model shown in Fig. 3, the deformations of fiber, matrix and interface in C/C composite under fiber indentation test were calculated. For the analysis of practical composites, the correlation between adjacent fibers must be taken into account, but in this study, two dimensional models were used for the first step of FEM examination including the interfacial debonding. So C/C composites reinforced with only single carbon fiber were used for this calculation, and the matrix phase was assumed to be carbon layer. The width of this layer was assumed to be 2 μm , that reflects a fiber volume fraction of specimen for fiber indentation test correctly (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3: FEM model of fiber indentation test

Fig. 4: Thickness of carbon layer around fiber

Under the indentation test, the effect of the area of contact between indenter tip and specimen on stress distribution was considered to be very large [10]. For this axis symmetrical FEM model, the shape of indenter tip was a cone not a triangular pyramid. Therefore, in this analysis, indenter tip was assumed to be a cone with 145.6 degrees of the apical angle so that the area of contact in case of the cone was as same as in case of the triangular pyramid at the same displacement of indenter, shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Shape of indenter tip

Interfacial Bonding Between Fiber and Matrix

Fig. 6 shows a typical example of TEM image at interface between fiber and matrix. A vertical direction of this figure is fiber direction. From this figure, the thickness of interface seems to be about 30 nm. And a structure of carbon at interface was observed to be graphite layers parallel to the fiber direction. That is, c-axis direction of this graphite was parallel to radial direction of the fiber. And, for graphite structure, bonding strength at c-axis direction is very weak because there are van der Waals' bonds between graphite layers [7]. So the debonding of fiber-matrix interface is considered to be as same as the debonding between the graphite layers.

Fig. 6: TEM image at interface between fiber and matrix

In the most previous analysis of micro indentation test, an extra interphase, which was made from reaction of fiber and matrix, was set up independently [12]. For C/C composites, the extra interphase seems to be the graphite layer. Now, in this FEM analysis, the graphite layers were assumed to be springs between nodes of fiber and matrix element in the FEM model. And debonding was assumed to occur when a length of the spring, that was 30 nm in the beginning of the FEM analysis, changed to 45 nm, which indicates that the distances between each graphite layers expand to one and half times. Where stiffness of the spring parallel and transverse to the fiber direction were determined to 50 GPa and 20 GPa, respectively, from mechanical properties of graphite [13].

And two kinds of the stress-transmission method in the spring were assumed to be as shown in Fig. 7 after the debonding at fiber-matrix interface. In Fig. 7, the case 1 is a usual method of the interfacial debonding on FEM analysis under the fiber indentation test. Under the condition of case 1 on the axis symmetrical FEM model, a debonding at one point on fiber surface seems to be equivalent to a debonding on one circumference of fiber surface including the debonding point. But this phenomena is considered not to exactly express a three dimensional phenomena of the debonding at fiber-matrix interface, because under the three dimension the debonding at one point on fiber surface seems to be gradually spread on the circumference including the debonding point. So a newly designed interfacial bonding was constructed shown in case 2 of Fig. 7. Under the condition of case 2, the bonding force of the spring between fiber and matrix was assumed to linearly decrease after the beginning of the interfacial debonding, that is considered to indicate the gradual spread of the interfacial debonding. That is, the interfacial bonding was presumed to yield not to fracture. And the slope of the bonding force in an unloading under the fiber indentation test was assumed to be as same as that in loading, because the bonding between fiber and matrix was considered to be supported by the residual bonding interface that has the same stiffness in both loading and unloading.

Fig. 7: Condition of debonding at fiber-matrix interface

Condition of FEM Model

After the fiber indentation test, the interfacial debonding and the indentation mark could not be observed at the specimen surface by SEM. So, in this FEM analysis, only the elastic deformations of fiber, matrix and C/C composites were considered. That is, the origin of the large hysteresis loop in Fig. 2 was assumed to be only an energy loss caused by the fiber-matrix interfacial debonding. The specimen holder and the indenter tip were presumed to be rigid. The condition of FEM analysis is as shown in Table 2. The Young's moduli of C/C

composite were determined from the measured values [14], except to the longitudinal Young's modulus of unidirectional C/C composites. The radial Young's modulus of fiber and the isotropic Young's modulus of matrix was assumed to be same as the transverse Young's modulus of unidirectional C/C composites. And the Poisson's Ratio and the shear modulus were determined from the previous researches [15] except for ν_{xy} and ν_{zx} of fiber, which was decided in reference of the Poisson's Ratio of composite and fiber.

On the other hand, the carbon fiber was considered to be mainly received the compressive stress at the fiber direction under the fiber indentation test, and the compressive Young's modulus of fiber has been reported to be the quarter of the tensile Young's modulus [16]. And the longitudinal Young's modulus of fiber are known to have the strain dependence. So the longitudinal Young's modulus of carbon fiber was assumed to be the quarter of the calculated value from the longitudinal Young's modulus of unidirectional C/C composites [14] according to the simple law of mixture, and the longitudinal Young's modulus of C/C composites was determined from this Young's modulus of fiber.

Table 2: Condition of FEM model

Analysis Model	Axis Symmetrical FEM Model
Specimen Size :	Radius 2500 μm , Thickness 80 μm
Radius of Fiber :	5 μm
Indenter Tip :	Cone with 145.6° of the Apical Angle
Thickness of Carbon Layer	:2 μm • (from Fiber Volume Fraction)
Elastic Properties of Each Element	
Fiber :	E_{xx} : 80GPa ν_{xy} :0.16 G_{xy} :10GPa E_{yy} : 8.9GPa ν_{yz} :0.30 G_{yz} :20GPa E_{zz} : 8.9GPa ν_{zx} :0.16 G_{zx} :10GPa Density 2.08 Mg/m ³
Carbon Layer :	E : 8.9GPa ν : 0.30 Density 1.70 Mg/m ³
C/C :	E_{xx} : 40GPa ν_{xy} :0.20 G_{xy} :8.9GPa E_{yy} : 8.9GPa ν_{yz} :0.30 G_{yz} :15GPa E_{zz} : 8.9GPa ν_{zx} :0.20 G_{zx} :8.9GPa Density 1.68 Mg/m ³

RESULTS OF FEM ANALYSIS

In this FEM analysis, only a displacement of indenter can be controlled. So the FEM analyses with the two kinds of interfacial bonding, that were case 1 and 2, were done in loading from 0 to 2.5 μm displacement of indenter and in unloading from 2.5 to 0 μm displacement. The indentation curves calculated from FEM model with the interfacial bonding of case 1 and 2 are shown in Fig. 8 (a) and (b), respectively. In Fig. 8 (a), the load was largely decreased over 0.6 μm displacement of indenter, and the interfacial debonding started after the 0.6 μm displacement in the FEM model with the interfacial bonding of case 1. But the large decrease of load was not detected in the experimental results. On the other hand, for the FEM model with the interfacial bonding of case 2, the load was continuously increased in loading although the interfacial debonding began after the 0.6 μm displacement. That is, the indentation curve of case 2 showed the hysteresis loop as same as the experimental results. So

the FEM model with the interfacial bonding of case 2 is considered to be suitable for the analysis of the fiber indentation test of C/C composites.

And, in this FEM analysis of case 2, the start point of the interfacial debonding was the inside not the surface of specimen. To put it in the concrete, the interfacial debonding started at the interface under 5 μm depth from the upper side of specimen surface. And the area of interfacial debonding gradually expanded into the lower side of specimen surface with increasing the displacement of indenter, but the interfacial debonding at both the upper and lower sides of specimen surface did not occur at the 2.5 μm displacement of indenter. This result from the FEM analysis was in good agreement with the result by the SEM observation of specimen surface after the fiber indentation test. Furthermore, in this FEM analysis of case 2, the maximum value of load at the 2.5 μm displacement of indenter was close to the experimental results. Therefore the compressive Young's modulus of carbon fiber in C/C composite was founded to be predictable from the FEM analysis with a newly designed interfacial bonding.

Fig. 8: Indentation curves calculated from FEM model with the interfacial bonding of case 1 (a) and case 2 (b)

CONCLUSIONS

To investigate the mechanism of the energy loss in the indentation curve under the fiber indentation test of C/C composites, the fiber indentation tests were performed and the indentation curve was analyzed by an axis symmetrical FEM model including a newly designed fiber-matrix interfacial bonding. The conclusions could be summarized as follows.

- (1) From the FEM analysis, the hysteresis loop was obtained in the indentation curve and the interfacial debonding was founded to start from the inside of specimen under fiber indentation test.
- (2) The indentation curve calculated by this FEM analysis was coincide with the experimental results, so the compressive Young's modulus of carbon fiber in C/C composite was founded to be predictable from this FEM analysis.

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